

Polarographic Studies on the Influence of Aqueous Mixtures of Some Organic Solvents on the Kinetics of Irreversible Electrode Reaction of Nitrobenzene

RAM RATAN and MUKHTAR SINGH

Chemical Laboratories, Agra College, Agra-282 002 (India)

Manuscript received 20 October 1978, revised 21 August 1979, accepted 9 February 1980

The polarographic behaviour of nitrobenzene in McIlvaine (McI) buffer of pH values 3.2 and 8 has been studied in the presence of aqueous mixtures of methanol, ethanol, dimethylformamide and acetonitrile. The reduction of nitrobenzene has been found to be diffusion-controlled and irreversible at different percentages of organic solvents. The kinetic parameters (αn_a and $k_{f,h}^0$) of irreversible electrode reaction of nitrobenzene have been calculated by Koutecky's method at different percentages of these organic solvents. A decrease in the value of kinetic parameters with increasing amounts of organic solvents indicates that the irreversible electrode reaction of nitrobenzene is rendered increasingly more irreversible. A negative shift in $E_{1/2}$ values and an increase in the value of ΔG^\ddagger , the free energy of activation, support this conclusion.

VIJAYALAKSHAMMA and Subrahmanya¹⁻³ have studied the polarographic behaviour of nitrobenzene in aqueous mixtures of ethanol, acetonitrile, acetone and dioxane with a view to determining the polarographic characteristics viz., $E_{1/2}$, i_d and D , as a function of the percentage of organic solvent. They have also calculated kinetic parameters for the irreversible electrode reaction of nitrobenzene at different percentages of these solvents. However, these studies are still incomprehensive in as much as that the influence of the organic content of the aqueous mixture on the kinetics of the electrode reaction has not been explained explicitly. With this aim in view a polarographic study of the electrode reaction of nitrobenzene in the presence of aqueous mixtures of methanol, ethanol, dimethylformamide and acetonitrile has been undertaken.

Materials and Methods :

All the chemicals used were either of A. R., B.D.H., or E. Merck, G. R. grade. The concentration of nitrobenzene was maintained at $1.0 \times 10^{-3} M$. Triton X-100 ($1.6 \times 10^{-5} \%$) was used as a maximum suppressor. A manual polarograph (Toshniwal, CL02) in conjunction with a polyflex galvanometer (Toshniwal, PL50) was used. All the measurements were made at $25 \pm 0.1^\circ$. Purified nitrogen was used for removing the dissolved oxygen. The potentials were measured against a saturated calomel electrode (S.C.E.). The d.m.e. had the following characteristics (in 0.1 M KCl, open circuit at 25°). $i_{corr} = 73.12$ cms, $t = 3.60$ sec, $m^{2/3} t^{1/6} = 2.672$ mg^{2/3} sec^{-1/2}.

The number of electrons (n) involved in the reduction process was determined by millicoulometric

method of DeVries and Kroon⁴ using a mercury pool cathode. This gave the value of n equal to 4 for the first step reduction and 2 for the second step. Having known the value of n , Ilkovic equation was used to calculate the value of D , the diffusion coefficient of nitrobenzene at different percentages of the organic solvents.

The potential dependent rate constant $k_{f,h}$ was calculated by Koutecky method^{5,6}. Having calculated $k_{f,h}$ at various stages of the wave, the parameters αn_a and $k_{f,h}^0$ were calculated from $\log k_{f,h}$ vs $E_{d.e.}$ plots⁷.

Results and Discussion

At pH 3.2 nitrobenzene in aqueous mixtures of ethanol (10%–50%) gives well defined 2-step reduction waves while at pH 8 only one step appears. The reduction mechanism at these pH values is as follows :

(I) At pH 3.2 and (II) at pH 8.

However, in the case of aqueous mixtures of methanol and dimethylformamide at pH 3.2 the second step does not appear at percentages ≥ 50 (Fig. 1) while in acetonitrile the second step does not appear at percentages ≥ 25 . At pH 8 one step reduction wave of nitrobenzene does not show any deformation as the percentage of the organic solvent is increased (Fig. 2).

The wave-heights are diffusion-controlled at all percentages of organic solvents as evidenced by the linearity of i_d vs $h_{\text{corr}}^{1/2}$ plots.

On applying various criteria of irreversibility⁸⁻¹⁰ it has been ascertained that the reduction of nitrobenzene is totally irreversible at different percentages of organic solvents.

Table 1 includes the polarographic characteristics of nitrobenzene in the presence of increasing percentages of organic solvents. A perusal of this table reveals that a significant negative shift in $E_{1/2}$ values occurs as the percentage of organic solvents is increased.

TABLE 1—POLAROGRAPHIC CHARACTERISTICS OF NITROBENZENE IN AQUEOUS MIXTURES OF ORGANIC SOLVENTS IN MCI BUFFER OF DIFFERENT pH VALUES

[Solvent] % (v/v)	i_d μA	I step $-E_{1/2}$ V (S.C.E.)	Slope mV	i_d μA	II step $-E_{1/2}$ V (S.C.E.)	Slope mV	$D \times 10^6$ $\text{cm}^2/\text{sec.}$
pH 3.2							
Dimethyl- formamide	10	17.56	0.33	82.14	4.08	0.88	3.89
	25	15.25	0.42	80.76	2.13	0.98	2.76
	50	14.55	0.58	118.18	-	-	1.65
pH 8							
Dimethyl- formamide	10	15.61	0.69	76.47	-	-	4.27
	25	15.25	0.80	90.00	-	-	4.08
	50	10.46	0.94	90.00	-	-	1.92
pH 3.2							
Ethanol	10	15.68	0.30	57.14	6.58	0.84	3.92
	25	14.97	0.35	70.00	6.10	0.91	3.50
	50	16.74	0.56	155.17	5.65	1.07	3.76
pH 8							
Ethanol	10	15.26	0.64	81.81	-	-	4.08
	25	13.13	0.70	77.77	-	-	3.02
	50	13.13	0.84	110.00	-	-	3.02
pH 3.2							
Acetonitrile	10	17.03	0.31	69.23	4.43	0.86	3.60
	25	20.58	0.39	90.90	-	-	3.30
	50	24.12	0.55	105.26	-	-	4.54
pH 8							
Acetonitrile	10	17.38	0.65	68.42	-	-	5.30
	25	17.74	0.74	75.00	-	-	5.52
	50	25.19	0.88	125.00	-	-	11.14
pH 3.2							
Methanol	10	18.08	0.29	70.58	6.16	0.78	4.70
	25	15.21	0.31	62.50	5.75	0.86	3.61
	50	20.55	0.43	109.90	-	-	7.40
pH 8							
Methanol	10	13.15	0.58	70.58	-	-	3.02
	25	12.74	0.64	70.00	-	-	2.82
	50	15.62	0.75	100.00	-	-	4.28

TABLE 2—VALUES OF KINETIC PARAMETERS (α , L^n_a AND $k_{f,h}^0$) AND OF ΔG^\ddagger IN AQUEOUS MIXTURES OF ORGANIC SOLVENTS IN MCI BUFFER OF DIFFERENT pH VALUES

[Solvent] % (v/v)	α_{n_a}	α	I step $k_{f,h}^0$ cm/sec	ΔG^\ddagger k cal mole ⁻¹	α_{n_a}	α	II step $k_{f,h}^0$ cm/sec	ΔG^\ddagger k. cal. mole ⁻¹
pH 3.2								
Dimethyl- formamide	10	0.68	0.38	7.60×10^{-6}	12.22	0.40	0.20	13.49
	25	0.59	0.29	6.29×10^{-6}	12.56	0.38	0.19	14.93
	50	0.35	0.27	7.26×10^{-7}	14.44	-	-	-
pH 8								
Dimethyl- formamide	10	0.76	0.38	9.12×10^{-9}	16.00	-	-	-
	25	0.60	0.30	1.92×10^{-9}	17.33	-	-	-
	50	0.57	0.28	6.48×10^{-11}	19.42	-	-	-
pH 3.2								
Ethanol	10	0.96	0.48	2.07×10^{-5}	10.93	0.59	0.29	16.00
	25	0.77	0.38	1.00×10^{-5}	11.84	0.52	0.26	16.80
	50	0.68	0.34	2.56×10^{-5}	12.87	0.48	0.24	19.61
pH 8								
Ethanol	10	0.73	0.36	1.03×10^{-8}	16.01	-	-	-
	25	0.64	0.32	6.05×10^{-9}	16.55	-	-	-
	50	0.53	0.26	3.04×10^{-9}	17.23	-	-	-
pH 3.2								
Acetonitrile	10	0.73	0.36	1.16×10^{-4}	8.94	0.35	0.17	15.14
	25	0.59	0.29	1.62×10^{-5}	10.64	-	-	-
	50	0.56	0.28	3.26×10^{-7}	14.39	-	-	-
pH 8								
Acetonitrile	10	0.78	0.39	3.82×10^{-9}	16.47	-	-	-
	25	0.70	0.35	1.25×10^{-10}	18.70	-	-	-
	50	0.51	0.25	1.00×10^{-10}	19.31	-	-	-
pH 3.2								
Methanol	10	0.78	0.39	3.88×10^{-5}	11.00	0.33	0.16	14.74
	25	0.72	0.36	2.34×10^{-5}	11.46	0.30	0.15	15.45
	50	0.51	0.25	8.63×10^{-6}	12.58	-	-	-
pH 8								
Methanol	10	0.80	0.40	4.78×10^{-9}	16.29	-	-	-
	25	0.74	0.37	9.42×10^{-10}	17.40	-	-	-
	50	0.66	0.33	8.69×10^{-10}	17.65	-	-	-

Fig. 1. Polarograms of nitrobenzene in different percentages of dimethylformamide at pH 3.2. (A) 10% (B) 25% (C) 50%

Fig. 2. Polarograms of nitrobenzene in different percentages of dimethylformamide at pH 8. (A) 10% (B) 25% (C) 50%

In Table 2 the values of kinetic parameters (αn_a and $k_{f,h}^o$) and also of ΔG^\ddagger have been listed. According to Vijayalakshamma and Subrahmanya¹, since n^a , the number of electrons involved in the rate determining step for nitrobenzene is 2, the value of α can be obtained from the corresponding values of αn_a at different percentages of organic solvents and these have been also included in Table 2. A perusal of this table shows that both α and $k_{f,h}^o$ record a decrease with increasing percentage of organic solvents thereby suggesting¹¹⁻¹⁴ that the electrode reaction of nitrobenzene is rendered increasingly more irreversible. A negative shift in $E_{1/2}$ and an increase in the value of ΔG^\ddagger , with increasing percentages of organic solvents lend support to this conclusion.

Acknowledgement

Thanks are due to the Principal, Agra College, Agra for providing necessary facilities.

References

1. S. K. VIJAYALAKSHAMMA and R. S. SUBRAHMANYA, *J. Electroanal. Chem.*, 1969, 23, 99.
2. S. K. VIJAYALAKSHAMMA and R. S. SUBRAHMANYA, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1971, 9, 1265.
3. S. K. VIJAYALAKSHAMMA and R. S. SUBRAHMANYA, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1976, 14A, 24.
4. T. DEVRIES and J. L. KROON, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 75, 2484.
5. J. KOUTECKY, *Chem. Listy*, 1953, 47, 323; *Colln. Czech. Chem. Commun.*, 1953, 18, 597.
6. J. KOUTECKY and J. CIZEK, *Colln. Czech. Chem. Commun.*, 1956, 21, 336.
7. J. E. STRASSNER and P. DELAHAY, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1952, 74, 6232.
8. L. MEITES, 'Polarographic Techniques', Interscience Publ., New York, 1965, p. 227.
9. R. GOTO and I. TACHI, *Proc. Intern. Polarogr. Congr.*, 1951, Vol. I, p. 69.
10. P. DELAHAY, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, 73, 4944; P. KIVALO, K. B. OLDHAM and H. A. LAITINEN, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 75, 4148.
11. S. K. JHA, S. JHA and S. N. SRIVASTAVA, *Z. Naturforsch.*, 1975, 30b, 859.
12. S. S. SHARMA, S. K. JHA and M. SINGH, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1977, 15A, 742.
13. S. S. SHARMA, S. K. JHA and M. SINGH, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1977, 15A, 923.
14. S. S. SHARMA, S. K. JHA and M. SINGH, *Z. Naturforsch.*, 1977, 32b, 416.